

IMPROVING VOCABULARY RANGE OF INTERMEDIATE LEVEL LEARNERS THROUGH EFFECTIVE APPLICATIONS.

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ABSTRACT

Language is becoming one of the predominant leading features which coming generation are expected to exclusively master and make it prevalent all over the world, therefore this article is devoted for those who have troubles in vocabulary expansion. The given online platforms below are highly likely to relieve the tension and make the process of acquisition more available and simpler.

INTRODUCTION

In this ever-developing world the role of English language in becoming fundamentally essential and being regarded as one of the widespread dominant languages which demand both teachers and learner to evoke strong enthusiasm for this language. This is an undeniable fact that, the majority of learners quit the process of gaining knowledge after facing basic challenges in widening the vocabulary span. According to (Kitajima, 2001) [1; 470- 483] vocabulary as one of the component skills seem to play crucial role in language achievement. It is assumed that labelling objects, everyday actions and basic concepts is possible while without vocabulary understanding it is impossible to say a single word. "Little can be transferred if one does know grammar, but nothing can be transferred if one does not know any vocabulary" (Wilkins, 1972) [3] which means the vocabulary span of the any language should be regarded equally as significant as the first blocks of a building. Words are the units of meaning which sentences, paragraphs and whole text is derived from. Moreover, language ability is expressed through the familiar number of words that highlight the fact that, teaching vocabulary is a critical area that needs paying special attention (Knight, 1994) [2; 285-299].

Undoubtedly technological advancements have greatly impacted on the way people live, making the hardships that was undergone by our ancestors simpler now. This tendency has the connection with the language acting as the modern aid for enhancing peoples' intentions to learn more. Nevertheless, several decades ago knowing the language was not as popular as now due to only less proportion of people were aware of ways and methods of language acquisition, the generation of 21st century can be named as geniuses of language.

The aim of this research is to shed the lights on several efficient ways of vocabulary expansion through the help of online applications. In the past people relied heavily on word for word direct translation or divided the page of the notebook into two parts, one which were written English words second part the transition into L2. Nonetheless now it is constantly suggested for those who higher level in language to memorize the word by either

its meaning and definition or antonym and synonym but for intermediate learners it might be a bit time demanding and challenging therefore the applications might greatly help them to learn unfamiliar words and phrases by heart with ease and interestingly in any place from mobile or laptop.

1. Word up

This platform offers 4 staged learning approach of English words, first stage emphasizes the section of testing yourself by a comprehensive self-assessment where the words that are unfamiliar can be selected in order not to waste extra time for the words which one has already mastered. The second stage is personalized leaning plan, according to the results of self-assessment, map is created with the gaps between, which will test existing knowledge. The given gaps should be focused on filling with individualized learning plan. In the third stage, examples from famous films or short extracts from speeches is provided in order to identify the most important words and its current meaning in use. Last stage is learning those new vocabulary with a full definition and specific context will be provided where the word or how it is used will be given.

2. Word of the day

Learning a new word every day helps to improve vocabulary range of learners' day by day and it is possible with this application which offers flashcard for each user with the definition and mostly children will enjoy learning a new word because it is suitable for ages four and up. However, as some could be complicated therefore while installing it is important to choose the category of words and level to learn. It is also suitable for people who always forget word revision or writing down new word due to busy schedules, because it offer the function of a reminder. New words of the day are reflected on the top of the screen every day.

3. WordPal

Fortunately, this app is available on the app store and can easily be installed on mobile and this application can be a bit challenging for young learners because the level of words is appropriate for intermediate level. WordPal increases vocabulary range of the learner trough synonym quizzes and demonstrating the definition for each word. There some words which have more than one meaning therefore in order to tackle with this tendency this app gives examples with the proper usage in sentence.

4. 7 Little words

Word memorization through context or situation lead to the long-term memory and this is puzzle game that teaches new words by letting you solve letter puzzles. There are five difficulty levels and a feature that allows you to choose between American, British or Australian English. Moreover, this platform is beneficial for those who want to study for an English exam and improve language skill before moving to a English Speaking country. In the instruction for this game it gives you 7 different words with various definition and lettered tiles to arrange into words and the purpose is that as you narrow down the choices from those you already know and still relax even being on mobile phone.

Indeed, now learners are provided with a great deal of opportunities which might help to boost vocabulary range even sitting at home without any tutorial no money is paid, the only things that is needed is internet connection and brain which is strongly motivated to expand knowledge. Although vocabulary at the fist glance can seem not as much as important as it is, in fact this is the section which needs to be focused first on order to be competent in lexical range.

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